

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

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Theories of change and influence pathways of forest- related public and private regulations

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report first analyzes the designed and expected theories of change of key policies and governance mechanisms regulating legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk commodity supply chains. This is based on an analysis of public and private regulations' goals, degree of compulsion, role of state and non-state actors, and designed pathways of influence on target groups. Second, the main intervention logics, understood as theories of policy and behavior change, are unpacked and the interactions between dominant and less dominant pathways of influence are assessed.

In short, this report shows that public policies and private governance mechanisms at the international level, at the EU, and the national level in Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon regulating forest and ecosystem-risk commodity supply chains rely on a combination of legally binding and non-binding intervention logics. We identified a dominant intervention logic such as (1.) rules or (2.) norms & discourses or (3.) markets or (4.) information & resources within each public policy and private governance mechanism. At the same time, the dominant intervention logics of most public and private instruments are (1.) rules and/or (3.) markets. However, the intervention logics of the analyzed public and private regulation often compete among each other, while a positive transformative impact would strongly rely on successfully implementing designed synergies and avoid contradictions with other intervention logics within the same instrument or other instruments.

INTRODUCTION

1992 marked the beginning of a stark increase in global environmental agreements, transnational nonstate market governance mechanisms, and state-sanctioned regulations to tackle deforestation, forest degradation, biodiversity loss, and climate change (Begemann et al., 2021; Lambin et al., 2018; Sotirov et al., 2020). Nevertheless, the increasingly strong demand for forestry (e.g., timber, pulp) and agricultural (e.g., cattle, oil palm, soya) commodities continues to cause deforestation, ecosystem degradation, and biodiversity loss, particularly in the tropics and subtropics (Pendrill et al., 2019a, 2019b). Forest and ecosystem-risk commodities (FERCs) are needed to meet a growing number and variety of societal consumption needs including food (e.g., food and beverage products) and non-food (e.g., soy for animal feed, oil palm for cosmetics, wood products for construction, biofuel and packaging) products. These compounding demands increase land use pressure and competition, adding to the governance complexity of sustainable land use, trade, and consumption (Bamière & Bellassen, 2018; Gaba, 2018). While (illegal) timber logging is the most important driver of (sub)tropical forest degradation (Hosonuma et al., 2012) and an important precursor to deforestation (Vancutsem et al., 2021), agriculture is the most important driver of global deforestation, driving 90%–99% of tropical forest loss (Pendrill et al., 2022).

In addition to environmental sustainability issues such as biodiversity loss and climate change, deforestation and forest degradation are linked with severe human rights violations (Global Witness, 2022; Human Rights Watch, 2019). Furthermore, forests worldwide provide income and livelihoods to rural communities and indigenous peoples (FAO & UNEP, 2020). However, deforestation and forest degradation associated with illegal activities in the forest sector and associated trade total to over US \$150 billion annually and result in huge economic losses for governments and market distortions for businesses (Nellemann and INTERPOL 2012). These telecoupled challenges connect demand- and supply-side regions through global FERC value chains in complex forms of mutual interdependencies (Lenschow et al., 2016).

As a response to these deforestation and forest degradation challenges, a variety of global, transnational and national public and private regulations have been developed and implemented to foster the protection and more sustainable management of forests (Begemann et al., 2021; Lambin et al., 2018; Sotirov et al. 2020). Despite this increased number of forest specific and forest related public and private regulations, why are deforestation, forest degradation, biodiversity loss, and greenhouse gas emissions from land use change still persisting issues?

Understanding how public policies and private governance mechanisms are designed to impact on target groups and regulate land use change can help in answering this question of (in-)effectiveness of public and private regulations in achieving explicitly stated policy goals (e.g., deforestation reductions) (Bernstein and Cashore 2012, Sotirov et al. 2020). As shown below, a key to understand the (in-)effectiveness of public and private regulations is to uncover their implicit or explicit theories of change.

By building on these and the below presented conceptualizations, in this report we address the following interrelated research questions:

- What are the designed and expected theories of change of key public regulations and private governance mechanisms regulating legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk commodity supply chains?
- What intervention logics prevail, and how do they interact?

With this, we can help address still existing empirical and theoretical knowledge gaps concerning the design and interactions of international, transnational, and (sub-)national forest related supply chain policies and governance mechanisms (e.g., Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Marques & Eberlein, 2021; van der Ven et al., 2021; Zeitin & Overdeest, 2021).

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this report are twofold. We first analyze the designed and expected theory of change of key policies and governance mechanisms regulating legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk commodity supply chains based on their goals, degrees of compulsion, and designed pathways of influence. Second, we further unpack their main intervention logics and assess interactions between different pathways of influence.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A key to understand the (in-)effectiveness of public and private regulations is to uncover their implicit or explicit theories of change. By design, public and private regulations incorporate implicit and explicit assumptions about problem definitions and problem solutions (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith 1999). These theories of change include a framework of ideas and standards that specifies not only the goals of policy and the different kinds of instruments that can be used to attain them, but also the very nature of the problems they are meant to be addressing (Hall 1993). This framework rests on basic value priorities, assumptions about physical and human nature, perceptions of important causal relationships, perceptions of world states including the magnitude of the problem, and perceptions and assumptions concerning the political priority and behavioral impacts of various policy instruments (Pressman and Wildavsky 1973). Thus public and private regulations can be conceptualized in much the same way as designed theories of policy and behavioral change (Majone 1980). This ability to map policies and theories of change on the same “canvas” also provides a vehicle for assessing the role and influence of state and non-state actors in policy and behavioral change over time (Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith 1999).

In line with grand social change theories like institutionalism (“I”), political economy (“E”), sociology and constructivism (“S”) and social psychology (“P”), public policies and private governance mechanisms rely on different intervention logics or pathways of influence towards policy and behavioral change (Cashore 2002, Bernstein and Cashore 2012; Deuffic et al. 2018). These include 1) rules (linked to “I”), 2) norms & discourses (linked to “S”), 3) market (dis)incentives (linked to “E”), and 4) information and resources (linked to “P”) (Bernstein & Cashore, 2012; Keohane, 1984; Keohane, 2002; Milner, 1997; Milner & Rosendorff, 1996). Furthermore, different pathways of influence interact within and across public and private regulations. Interactions can be symmetrical, asymmetrical, antagonistic, synergistic, intentional, or unintentional (Bernstein & Cashore, 2012; Eberlein et al., 2014).

This report applies an adapted version of Bernstein and Cashore’s (2012) theoretical framework of four global pathways of influence on domestic and company-level policy change to identify and assess the policies and governance mechanisms’ theories of change (Figure 1). The framework describes pathways through which processes at the international level can influence and change policy development at the national level and in business organizations. The original four pathways are 1) international rules, 2) international norms and discourses, 3) international markets, and 4) direct access to domestic policy processes. The following sections explain the different pathways and our adapted theoretical framework.

Figure 1: Pathways of influence and direction of influence.

The *rules pathway* refers to the traditional focus of institutionalism (“I”), incl. regime effectiveness literature, where substantive rules (e.g., objectives, implementation instruments, reporting and verification commitments), are eventually codified as legally binding rules (e.g., hard law treaties, hybrid governance regimes, private standards) for state and non-state actors. They are mostly enforced by state authorities and to be implemented by both state and non-state actors as regulatory targets. (Non-)compliance with hard laws (e.g., regulations) can be enforced through sanctions and penalties (e.g., in administrative or criminal courts). Regardless of their enforcement, rules are expected to create a compliance pull due to their general acceptance as legal and/or legitimate rules. Actors change their policy and firm-level behaviour due to logic of appropriateness to follow the rules (Bernstein and Cashore, 2012; Sotirov et al., 2020).

In line with sociology and constructivism (“S”), the *norms and discourses pathway* posits that societal norms (e.g., environmental protection, sustainable forest management, sustainable value chains) can influence the direction of policy and behavioral change even if they are not codified in hard laws. Powerful and influential agents of normative change, such as policy advocates and policy entrepreneurs (e.g., environmental NGOs, business organizations, scientists, think tanks, and consultants), promote different societal norms to define and regulate appropriate domestic behavior. Norms and discourses are often not (yet) formally institutionalized or codified in hard law and predominantly appear in the form of social pressure (e.g., public opinion, civil society), non-binding soft law (e.g., normative expectations, ideologies) or cultural discourses and practices (problem definitions, problem solutions). Compliance with soft law (e.g., strategies, guidelines) cannot be enforced through legal procedures imposing penalties and sanctions. Actors change their regulatory and economic behavior based on normative pressure (e.g., naming and shaming campaigns), moral values (e.g., legality and sustainability norms), and internalization of powerful discourses (e.g., corporate social responsibility) (e.g., Abbott et al., 2021; Bernstein and Cashore, 2012; Cashore, 2002; Hix & Høyland, 2011; Sotirov et al., 2020).

In line with political economy (“E”), the *markets pathway* refers to how domestic policy and behavioral change processes take place through positive or negative economic incentives. Global market mechanisms, trade, and

supply chain interventions work with market demand, market access, revenues, price premiums, compensation payments, and company recognition. Market-creating interventions include economic carrots in the form of incentive-based instruments (e.g., certification, eco-labeling, price premiums, public and private procurement, free trade partnership agreements, payments for ecosystem services, and firm recognition with a social license to operate). Market correcting interventions use economic sticks in the form of market disincentives (e.g., consumer boycotts, voluntary moratoria by economic operators, trade licensing regimes, risk based due diligence, production quotas, consumption taxes, and custom duties). The markets pathway posits that dependence on foreign markets and consumption decisions by aware consumers determine policy influence. Actors change their policy and firm-level behaviour in the logic of consequences to capture material benefits and/or avoid substantial costs (Bernstein and Cashore, 2012; Sotirov et al., 2020).

In line with social psychology ("P"), the *direct access pathway* rests on a knowledge-based logic and works with policy diffusion/know-how and technology transfer, including international development cooperation. While aiming to respect the national context and sovereignty, this pathway changes the policy and company-level behavior of actors through education, training, assistance, capacity building, and co-governance via participatory dialogues and partnerships between domestic and international public and private actors and authorities, often supported by matching funding. Changes of the behavior of domestic policy and business actors takes place through the diffusion of knowledge, such as policy ideas, business models, and management technologies (Bernstein and Cashore, 2012; Sotirov et al., 2020). Drawing on international relations scholarship (e.g., Keohane, 1984; Keohane, 2002; Milner, 1997; Milner & Rosendorff, 1996), we further develop this pathway towards an *information and resources pathway* to enhance the framework's applicability to analyze demand-side and supply-side public and private regulations (cf. Schleifer, 2023). The information and resources pathway, building on and further developing the direct access pathway, keeps with the main logic of knowledge-based changes (e.g., capacity building, data sharing) and resources (e.g., financial support, technologies) shared or incentivized as part of a policy or governance mechanism.

Empirically, we apply the slightly adapted pathways of influence framework to analyze two internal action-oriented (i.e., domestically within the EU, and domestically in Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon) and two external action-oriented directions of influence (i.e., EU to supply-side countries, and vice-versa). Due to the strong reference to development cooperation, the direct access pathway is not pertinent for analyzing influences from the supply-side to the demand-side (i.e., EU) (Figure 1). Development cooperation is based on a historical relationship of economically developed countries supporting developing countries in need (Degnbol-Martinussen & Engberg-Pedersen, 2003) and would mainly cater to one direction of policy and knowledge transfer (i.e., demand-side to supply-side). Furthermore, south-south cooperation is increasing in the multilateral arena, and domestic policies can also influence international policy-making (Gray & Gills, 2016; Marques & Eberlein, 2021; Schleifer, 2023; van der Ven et al., 2021). In line with international relations scholarship, we adapted the fourth pathway as the

“information and resources pathway” (see above).

All four pathways of change and their underlying theories of change – namely the rules (“I”), norms & discourses (“S”), markets (“E”), and information & resources (“P”) - can have a domestically-oriented influence on actors’ policy and corporate behavior both on the demand side (e.g., in the EU), and on the supply side (e.g. in tropical producer countries). They can also have an externally-oriented influence from the demand side to the supply side or from the supply side to the demand side.

Importantly, interactions of mechanisms and processes within and across the different pathways of influence can create collective influences. However, little is known about how the different pathways influence each other and work together (Bernstein and Cashore, 2012). Emerging research finds however that different pathways (e.g., rules vs. markets) sometimes work against each other, sometimes with each other (Sotirov et al. 2020). This is known in the literature as policy (in-)coherence (Sotirov et al. 2022) or regime fragmentation (Begemann et al. 2021) or institutional bricolage that contributes to overall policy (in-)effectiveness

METHODS

Empirically, this report builds on Sotirov et al. (2020) and Berning et al.'s (2023a; b) mapping and classification of key public and private policies and governance mechanisms regulating legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk commodity supply chains across demand and supply-side countries and regions. This mapping follows a matrix describing different types of public policies and private governance mechanisms concerning three variables: degree of compulsion, direct participation of actors, and geographical scope, first developed and applied in Sotirov et al. (2020).

We first identified key examples of policies and governance mechanisms from these overarching types based on a review of the state-of-the-art research, gray literature, and policy and legislative documents. The main geographical focus areas and units for analysis to identify relevant public policies and private governance mechanisms were the EU (as a major consumer and trader of FERCs) and Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon (as relevant FERC producers), all selected as case studies in the CLEVER research project (<https://clever-project.eu/>).

Legally-binding policies and governance mechanisms include the Paris Agreement at the international level, the EU-Mercosur free trade agreement (draft) at the transnational level, and several (sub-)national¹ initiatives in Brazil (Brazil Forest Code and Brazil Environmental Crime Law), Cameroon (Cameroon Forestry Law, Cameroon Forest Law Enforcement, Governance and Trade (FLEGT) Voluntary Partnership Agreement (VPA) Timber Legality

¹ This refers to national (i.e., country-level) policies and governance mechanisms and/or subnational (i.e., local level) initiatives.

Assurance System (TLAS)), and Gabon (Gabon Forest Code, Gabon Mandatory Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) certification).

A specific key subsection of *legally-binding transnational public initiatives* include the EU Timber Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 995/2010), EU FLEGT Regulation (Council Regulation (EC) No 2173/2005), which allows for the control of timber entering the EU from countries entering into EU-partner country FLEGT VPAs (e.g., EU-Indonesia FLEGT VPA), and the EU Regulation on deforestation-free products (Regulation (EU) 2023/1115).

Non-legally binding policies and governance mechanisms include the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) at the international level, the EU FLEGT Action Plan & EU-partner country Forest Partnerships, Central African Economic and Monetary Community (CEMAC) log export ban, and Belém Declaration at the transnational level, and the Interstate Consortium for the Sustainable Development of the Legal Amazon at the supranational² level.

Under private law³ legally binding private initiatives include transnational certification schemes (e.g., FSC) and the subnational Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium. Companies can voluntarily decide if they enter into a contractual agreement with certifiers or whether they request adherence to private sourcing standards from upstream suppliers. Albeit voluntary at first, certified organizations or suppliers can be audited by third-party organizations once there is an agreement and private contract in place. They can be punished for noncompliance through, for instance, certification withdrawal or by losing a buyer. *Non-legally binding transnational private initiatives* include the Consumer Goods Forum Forest Positive Coalition, where partners voluntarily form a coalition around shared goals and commitments without sanctionable contractual arrangements.

Second, we analyzed the designed and expected theories of change of these public policies and private governance mechanisms by drawing on key theory-derived analytical categories as introduced in the theoretical chapter (see also Figure 1). In this report, we focus on analyzing their underlying drivers by first identifying their desired and expected outcomes based on an analysis of their stated goals (e.g., deforestation reductions, biodiversity conservation). Second, we unpack their theory of change concerning achieving the desired and expected outcomes by analyzing their main pathways of influence. We identify whether the selected public policies and private governance mechanisms primarily rely on the rules (e.g., hard standards and enforcement mechanisms), norms and discourses (e.g., normative pressure), markets (e.g., economic (dis)incentives), and/or the information and resources (e.g., capacity building) pathway of influence. These are rooted in the different grand social change theories ("I", "E", "S" and "P") mentioned above. Third, we further unpack their main intervention logics by assessing how the different intervention logics interact.

² "Supranational" refers to ceding or sharing decision-making authority with an organization or body that operates above the national level for a group of member states.

³ Private law refers to private contracts regulating relationships between private parties (e.g., individuals and organizations)

RESULTS

The following sections detail the key goals, degree of compulsion (i.e., legally binding vs. non-legally binding), and designed pathways of influence of the selected policies and governance mechanisms. Each section analyzes the designed rules, norms and discourses, markets, and information and resources pathways and how the different pathways interact. Table 1 provides an overview of the most prominent and supporting intervention logics within each policy and governance mechanism. Under the markets pathway, the cells shaded in green relate to a logic of market incentive, while those shaded in orange relate to a logic of market disincentive. Figure 2 maps the relationship between the different policies and governance mechanisms.

Table 1: Overview of intervention logics of selected forest related public policies and private governance mechanisms (*X* = dominant intervention logic; *(X)* = additional key intervention logic; *°* = supporting intervention logic; orange cells = market disincentive, green cells = market incentive).

Public policies and private governance mechanisms analyzed	Overview of pathways of influence			
	Rules	Norms & discourses	Markets	Information & resources
Paris Agreement	(X)	X	°	(X)
Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework	°	X	°	(X)
EU Timber Regulation	X	°	(X)	°
EU Regulation on deforestation-free products	X	°	(X)	°
EU FLEGT Regulation & EU-partner country FLEGT VPAs	(X)	°	X	X
EU-Mercosur free trade agreement (draft)	(X)	°	X	°
Certification in the forest and agricultural sector (e.g., FSC/PEFC, RTRS)	(X)	(X)	X	°
(Sub-)national private regulation (e.g., Brazil Amazon Soy Moratorium)	(X)	(X)	X	°
Industry self-regulation (e.g., Consumer Goods Forum Forest Positive Coalition)	°	°	X	(X)
Forest Partnerships	°	(X)	(X)	X

Analyzed policies and governance mechanisms	Rules	Norms & discourses	Markets	Information & resources
CEMAC log export ban ⁴	(X)	X	°	°
Belém Declaration	°	X	°	°
Brazil: The Native Vegetation Protection Law (Forest Code)	X	°	°	°
Brazil: Environmental Crime Law	X	°	°	°
Cameroon: Forestry Law	X	°	°	
Cameroon: FLEGT VPA & TLAS system	(X)	°	X	°
Gabon: Forest Code	X	°	°	
Gabon: Mandatory FSC certification	(X)	°	X	°
Interstate Consortium for the Sustainable Development of the Legal Amazon	°	X	°	(X)

⁴ Upon adoption in national law, the rules pathway becomes the main intervention logic.

International hard laws: the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD), and the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) with the 1997 Kyoto Protocol and the 2015 Paris Agreement

International soft laws: non-binding UN conferences, agendas, and frameworks including the 1972 Stockholm Declaration, 1987 Sustainable Development Brundtland Report, 1992 UN Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED) in Rio (Agenda 21) and following 2002 Summit, 2000 Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), 2015 UN Agenda 2030 on Sustainable Development (Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)), and the 2022 Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF)

Forest-related international soft laws:

International Arrangement on Forests (IAF), the UN Forum on Forests (UNFF), the UNFF Secretariat, the UNFF Global Forest Financing Facilitation Network (GFFFN), the UNFF Trust Fund, the UN Strategic Plan for Forests (UNSPF), the UN Forest Instrument, the concepts on Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) and Criteria and Indicators (C&I), REDD+, the 2014 New York Declaration on Forests (NYDF), 2021 Glasgow Leaders' Declaration on Forests and Land Use (GDFLU)

Figure 2: Relationship between the policies and governance mechanisms (own illustration).

1. International regulatory governance

1.1 Paris Agreement (hard law)

In 2015, the parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) signed the Paris Agreement (FCCC/CP/2015/10/Add.1), an international legally binding agreement that entered into force in 2016 (*rules pathway, Table 1*). Key state (e.g., UN member states) and non-state actors (e.g., NGOs, scientific community) have long advocated for concrete measures to combat climate change (IPCC, 2018; Richardson et al., 2023; Rockström et al., 2009). The Paris Agreement's rules institutionalize the international norm of tackling, mitigating, and adapting to climate change in the form of a global response. The agreement has the following legally-binding objectives: 1) mitigation measures: halting the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels; 2) adaptation measures: increasing the ability to adapt to the adverse impacts of climate change and foster climate resilience and low greenhouse gas emissions development, in a manner that does not threaten food production; and, 3) financing for implementation: making finance flows consistent with a pathway towards low greenhouse gas emissions and climate-resilient development (Art. 2) (*norms & discourses and rules pathways*).

Internationally negotiated and adopted by state actors, they are the main actors responsible for implementing the Paris Agreement. Non-state actors also play an important role in achieving its policy objectives. For instance, the Paris Agreement encourages public-private partnerships for its implementation (Art. 6), and works with organizations, such as the Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) Partnership (NDC Partnership, 2023), to enhance technology transfer (Art. 10), capacity building and information exchange (Art. 11) (*markets and information & resources pathways*). The Agreement's implementation strongly depends on facilitating finance flows (Art. 9), which in practice is orchestrated through the Global Environment Facility (GEF) and the Green Climate Fund (GCF) (*markets pathway*). Both demand- and supply-side countries are expected to comply with the Agreement. However, by addressing UNFCCC's norm of "Common But Differentiated Responsibilities" (Art. 2), the Agreement states that developing countries need greater support to implement the agreement, especially financially (Art. 9) (*norms & discourses pathway*).

The member states signatories to the Agreement are obliged to comply by institutionalizing the obligations in their domestic laws and policies. The first step to this institutionalization is the submission of their NDC, which communicates concrete measures to be achieved by 2030 (e.g., regarding renewable energy transition, land use change, economic diversification, and disaster risk management) (Art. 3). The NDCs must be updated every five years (Art. 4) and parties are required to provide biennial reports under a framework for transparency (Art. 13). If the agreed NDC is not institutionalized in domestic law, the member state will be found to be non-compliant. However, there will be no direct punishment or sanction since the UN has no power of coercion to enforce compliance (Pauwelyn, 2003; Streck,

2023) (*limited rules pathway, Table 1*). However, several mechanisms seek to facilitate the Agreement's implementation and compliance. This includes the annual Conference of the Parties (COP) and its expert Committee (Art. 15), taking stock of the Agreement's implementation and highlighting non-compliance by publicly reporting how countries have progressed (or not) in reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Art. 14) (*rules and norms & discourses pathways*). Therefore, member states primarily seek compliance with the Paris Agreement based on the UN's normative power and transparency mechanisms that can be seen as a naming and shaming mechanism and not because of fears of punishment through hard laws (*norms & discourses pathway*).

Specifically related to forests, the Paris Agreement encourages the implementation of the Warsaw Framework for REDD+, established in 2013, in Article 5. Albeit indirectly mentioned as a mechanism under the Paris Agreement, the framework itself is non-legally binding. The acronym stands for "reducing emissions from deforestation and forest degradation in developing countries, plus additional forest-related activities that protect the climate, namely sustainable management of forests and the conservation and enhancement of forest carbon stocks" (UNFCCC, 2023) (*rules and norms & discourses pathway*).

REDD+ seeks to make the maintenance of tropical forests economically more valuable than their conversion to an alternative land use. The logic is that this would deter deforestation and forest degradation and create opportunities for financially valuing carbon storage. In return, countries participating in REDD+ would receive payments for verified/certified emission reductions and removals (*markets pathway*). Given the complexity of forest carbon accounting and the lack of an agreed global carbon market, REDD+ has revealed implementation challenges and is still to show its effectiveness, and forests remain at the center of the Convention's annual discussions (Sotirov et al., 2020).

1.2 Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (soft law)

Key state (e.g., UN member states) and non-state actors (e.g., NGOs, the scientific community) have long advocated for urgent measures to protect biodiversity (Rockström et al., 2009; IPBES, 2019). The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) rules institutionalize this biodiversity protection-oriented norm in its main legally-binding objectives (e.g., the conservation of biological diversity, the sustainable use of its components, and the fair and equitable sharing of the benefits arising out of the utilization of genetic resources) (*rules pathway*). This was followed by the Aichi Biodiversity Targets (Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011- 2020), which were largely unmet (Streck, 2023).

In December 2022, the parties to the CBD adopted the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) (CBD/COP/DEC/15/4), an international non-legally binding agreement, as it was not ratified by member states. The GBF formalizes the international norm of tackling biodiversity loss through 23 action-oriented global targets for urgent action until 2030 (e.g., reducing threats to biodiversity, meeting people's needs through sustainable use and

benefit-sharing, tools, and solutions for implementation and mainstreaming) with four overall goals to be achieved by 2050. These goals are related to the integrity and resilience of all ecosystems, the sustainable use and management of biodiversity, the monetary and non-monetary use of genetic resources, and adequate means of implementation, including financial resources, capacity-building, and technical and scientific cooperation. It further recognizes the urgent political commitment of all governance levels (e.g., global, regional, national) to achieve sustainable development and reduce and reverse the drivers of biodiversity loss (Section E) (*norms & discourses pathway, Table 1*).

Under international law, this non-binding agreement contains political and moral commitments as soft rules but does not intend to create legal rights and obligations (Patrick, 2015; Abbott & Snidal, 2021) (*norms and discourses pathway*). At the same time, the GBF is observed and managed under the CBD, which is legally binding to its member states (*rules pathway*). The GBF explicitly promotes coherence with other existing multilateral agreements, such as the Paris Agreement and the 2030 Agenda (Sections B and D). Internationally negotiated and decided by state actors, they are the main actors responsible for its implementation. Non-state actors are expected to play a particularly important role in achieving its goals and targets. The GBF explicitly takes on a “whole-of-government and whole-of-society” approach, which means that it expects all levels of government and all actors of society to be engaged in its implementation (Section C). Furthermore, in its considerations of implementation (Section C), concrete socio-environmental norms and values are highlighted (e.g., contributions and rights of indigenous peoples and local communities, Mother Earth’s value systems, the right to development, human rights, gender equality, intergenerational equity) (*norms and discourses pathway*).

Capacity building, exchange of information, as well as technical and scientific cooperation are also expected through South-South, North-South, and triangular cooperation (i.e., involving two or more developing countries and the support of one or more developed countries or multilateral organizations) (UNOSSC, 2023) (Target 20). Furthermore, the GBF lists specific actions for communication, education, awareness, and uptake of its targets (Section K) (*information & resources pathway*). In terms of market incentives, target 19 states that there should be substantial and progressively increased levels of financial resources to implement national biodiversity strategies, amounting to at least USD 200 billion per year by 2030 (*markets pathway*). Equitable access to financial resources, capacity-building, technical, and scientific cooperation to implement the GBF is also recognized, especially to developing country Parties, particularly least developed countries, small island states, and economies in transition (Goal D) (*information and resources pathway*).

Albeit not legally-binding, the GBF institutionalizes compliance assurance mechanisms through soft rules. Signatory countries must establish National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) in alignment with the Framework and should produce national reports, which go through voluntary peer reviews (Section J) (*rules pathway*). As portrayed, this governance mechanism primarily relies on the norms and discourses pathway in its designed theory to influence behavioral change (Table 1).

2. Transnational hybrid regulation

2.1 EU Timber Regulation

In 2003 the EU adopted the FLEGT Action Plan, which led to the development of two EU laws regulating timber legality. The FLEGT Regulation (Council Regulation No 2173/2005) allows for controlling timber imports to the EU from partner countries that entered into bilateral FLEGT Voluntary Partnership Agreements (VPAs). Partner countries must set up national timber legality licensing and assurance systems (TLAS) to reap EU market benefits under EU-partner country FLEGT VPAs (see section 3.1). The EU Timber Regulation (EU Regulation No 995/2010, EUTR) is a demand-side legally-binding market-correcting trade regulation with the objective of fighting against illegal logging and related trade (Recital 31). The EUTR was adopted in 2010, entered into application in 2013 (Sotirov et al. 2017), and will be repealed by the 2023 EU Regulation on Deforestation-free products with effect from 30 December 2024 (see section 2.2) (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024) (*rules pathway*).

Key public (e.g., EU and Member State officials) and private actors (e.g., NGOs) carry and advocate for timber legality and sustainability norms (Humphreys, 2006; Leipold et al., 2016). The EUTR institutionalized the international norm of fighting against illegal timber production, trade, and consumption in the form of a legality standard as defined by producer countries (Sotirov et al., 2017). Under the EUTR, illegally harvested timber is defined as timber harvested in contravention of the applicable legislation in the country of harvest. The applicable legislation refers to producer countries' legislation concerning timber harvesting-related rights, payments, duties, laws, and third-party legal use and tenure rights, as well as forest sector trade and customs laws (Art. 2). This legality standard specifically excludes sustainability to respect producer countries sovereignty (Overdevest & Zeitlin, 2014; Zeitlin & Overdevest, 2021) (*norms & discourses and rules pathways*).

The EUTR's main intervention logic primarily relies on two key market-correcting instruments. First, the EUTR prohibits placing illegally sourced timber and timber products on the EU market. Second, operators that first place timber and timber products on the EU market must exercise due diligence along their supply chains to ensure negligible risk of illegality. The three-tiered due diligence system includes information documentation, risk assessment, and risk mitigation obligations. Traders (i.e., those who make timber and timber products available on the EU market) must comply with traceability requirements (e.g., documentation of buyer and seller identifying information) (Sotirov et al. 2017; Berning and Sotirov, 2023; Köthke et al., 2023) (*rules pathway, Table 1*).

The EUTR's market-correcting instruments to disincentivize trade in illegally produced timber and timber products are combined with market-building mechanisms to incentivize trade in legally sourced timber and timber products. First, FLEGT-licensed timber is considered to have been legally harvested under the EUTR, fulfilling the operators' due diligence requirements, therefore providing a green lane market advantage (Sotirov et al. 2017). Second, the EUTR recognizes private regulation (i.e., third-party

verified schemes such as certification) as a tool that may support the EUTR's risk assessment and mitigation obligations, but without granting a green lane market advantage (Dieguez and Sotirov, 2021; Köthke et al., 2023) (*markets pathway, Table 1*).

Non-compliance with the EUTR's prohibition clause, due diligence, traceability, and reporting obligations can be enforced through penalties, which may include fines, the seizure of timber and timber products, and trade authorization suspensions (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Köthke et al., 2023) (*rules pathway*).

Additionally, third parties (e.g., NGOs) can submit substantiated concerns about detected implementation shortcomings to competent authorities to trigger enforcement actions. Under the EUDR, this civil society co-governance mechanism has been strengthened by creating follow-up obligations for competent authorities (see section 2.2). Furthermore, competent authorities should make records of checks and related relevant information available to the public to ensure transparency (*norms & discourses and information & resources pathways*) (Sotirov et al. 2017).

To support producer countries in meeting the EUTR's timber legality standard, the FLEGT Action Plan foresees EU support in the form of EU-partner country FLEGT VPAs (Overdevest & Zeitlin, 2014; Zeitlin & Overdevest, 2021) (*information & resources pathway*) (see section 3.1).

2.2 EU Regulation on Deforestation-free products

To close regulatory gaps in the EU's forest-related legislative framework and to more directly address the EU's impact on global deforestation and forest degradation, including that driven by agricultural FERC production, trade, and consumption, the EU adopted the EU Regulation on deforestation-free products (Regulation (EU) 2023/1115, EUDR) that entered into force on 29 June 2023. The EUDR will enter into application from 30 December 2024, with an additional six months provided for compliance by operators that are micro or small undertakings (Art. 38). The new regulation will repeal the EUTR with effect from 30 December 2024⁵ (Sotirov et al. 2022; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024; Köthke et al., 2023) (*rules pathway*).

The new regulation's main objective is to prevent the placement and making available on (or export from) the Union market of products associated with deforestation or forest degradation (Art. 1). The EU thereby seeks to reduce global deforestation, EU-driven greenhouse gas emissions, and biodiversity loss to achieve the European Green Deal's 2050 climate neutrality and biodiversity loss reduction goals (Art. 1, Recital 13). The EU also seeks to promote Union-wide and global sustainable production and consumption patterns (Recital 18; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024).

Key state (e.g., EU and Member State officials) and non-state actors (e.g.,

⁵ However, the EUTR continues to apply until 31 December 2027 to timber and timber products produced before 29 June 2023 and placed on the Union market from 30 December 2024.

NGOs) carry and advocate for FERC legality, sustainability, and human rights norms (Berning & Sotirov, 2024). The EUDR institutionalized the forest-risk commodity (FRC) sustainability norm in the form of a deforestation-free definition (with the possibility to extend the scope to include other natural ecosystems as part of the Review process, Art. 34). The EUDR goes beyond the previous EUTR focus on regulating timber legality as defined by producer countries (see sections 2.1 and 3.1) by requiring that relevant products are i) deforestation-free, ii) produced legally according to the relevant legislation in the country of production and iii) covered by a due diligence statement (Art. 3). Deforestation-free means that relevant commodities were produced on land that has not been subject to deforestation, and that wood has been harvested from the forest without inducing forest degradation, after the retroactive cut-off date of 31 December 2020. Deforestation is defined as “the conversion of forest to agricultural use, whether human induced or not.” Forest degradation is defined as “structural changes to forest cover, taking the form of the conversion of: (a) primary forests or naturally regenerating forests into plantation forests or into other wooded land; or (b) primary forests into planted forests” (Art. 2; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Köthke et al., 2023) (*norms & discourses and rules pathways*).

The EUDR institutionalized a more comprehensive legality standard than the EUTR. The EUTR prohibits the placing on the Union market for the first time of illegally harvested timber (i.e., harvested in contravention of the applicable legislation in the country of harvest) or timber products derived from such timber (see section 2.1). The EUDR prohibits the import, but also the intra-EU trade and export, of FRCs and derived products if they have been produced in contravention of the relevant legislation of the country of production. This includes applicable laws concerning the legal status of the area of FRC production in terms of land use rights, environmental protection and forest-related rules, third parties’ rights, labor rights, tax, anti-corruption, trade and customs regulations, human rights protected under international law, and the principle of free, prior and informed consent. The EUDR thereby institutionalized more comprehensive human rights standards; whereas the EUTR was more specific concerning applicable harvesting-related legislation (Art. 2; Berning and Sotirov, 2023; Köthke et al., 2023) (*rules pathway*).

The EUDR establishes an EUTR-like but expanded prohibition clause and more detailed due diligence obligations to implement and enforce these normative standards. The EUDR prohibits importing, exporting, and trading of relevant products that contain, have been fed with or have been made using seven FRCs (i.e., cattle, cocoa, coffee, oil palm, rubber, soya, and wood), including certain derived products (e.g., chocolate, leather, furniture, printed paper) unless the deforestation-free, legality, and due diligence statement submission obligations are fulfilled (see above) (*rules pathway*).

Additionally, the EUDR further develops the due diligence obligations (e.g., new geolocation requirements, detailed specifications for information collection and criteria to consider during the risk assessment) and ensures that actors along the EU supply chain are responsible for compliance. The EUDR obliges importers, exporters, and large traders (i.e., large enterprises that make products available on the EU market) to exercise risk-based due diligence to assess and mitigate risks along their supply chains; whereas the

EUTR only requested due diligence from first placers (see section 2.1). At the same time, the EUDR introduced new due diligence simplifications for SME operators (e.g., the possibility to refer to existing due diligence statements) (Berning & Sotirov, 2024; Köthke et al., 2023) (*rules pathway*).

Compared to the EUTR, the EUDR relies on a stronger state-based regulatory approach. First, FLEGT-licensed wood is no longer granted a green lane to the EU market as it only fulfills the EUDR's timber legality requirement but not the new deforestation-free standard. Similarly, the green lane for timber covered by Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES) permits has also been removed. The acceptance of FLEGT licenses as proof of timber legality but not sustainability (i.e., deforestation-free) seeks to respect bilateral commitments, preserve progress achieved with partner countries that reached the FLEGT licensing stage (i.e., Indonesia), and support current VPA partners in reaching this stage. Second, third-party verified schemes (e.g., forest certification) are now only permitted as an auxiliary tool to support the EUDR's risk assessment obligations if they fulfill the EUDR's information requirements (Recital 81; Art. 10; Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024) (*rules and markets pathways*).

To address EUTR-related implementation and enforcement shortcomings in EU Member States (e.g., inconsistent implementation and enforcement across Member States (McDermott & Sotirov, 2018; Köthke and Sotirov, 2023), the EUDR introduced several innovations (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024; Köthke et al. 2023). First, the EUDR requests the mandatory submission of due diligence statements electronically through a new centralized information system, visible to competent authorities and customs. The new tool is expected to be essential in supporting the 1) identification of operators and trades, 2) detection of higher-risk economic activities, and 3) planning inspections. Second, the EUDR introduced new risk-based minimum inspection obligations and a new enforcement cost reclaim mechanism for competent authorities, empowers competent authorities to take immediate interim measures (e.g., after receiving substantiated concerns), entitles third parties to review the processing of substantiated concerns by competent authorities, and introduces a new country benchmarking system. This deforestation and forest degradation risk-rating system – categorizing producer countries and regions as low, standard, or high risk – foresees simplified due diligence requirements for operators and traders sourcing relevant products from areas with a low risk rating and expanded obligations for EU Member States' competent authorities to conduct more mandatory compliance checks in the case of a high risk and standard risk rating. The EUDR also establishes that Member States' rules on dissuasive penalties must include fines where the maximum fine must be at least 4% of the operators' or trader's annual turnover in the EU. Penalties must also include the confiscation of products and revenues, a temporary exclusion from public procurement processes and public funding access, temporary prohibitions to import, trade, and export FRCs, and the prohibition to exercise simplified due diligence (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; 2024) (*rules pathway*).

Additionally, the EUDR obliges the Commission to cooperate with producer countries to address deforestation and forest degradation and support them in meeting the EUDR's FRC production standards, for instance, through Forest Partnerships (*information & resources pathway*) (Art. 30; Berning & Sotirov,

2023; 2024).

3. Transnational free trade agreements

3.1 EU FLEGT Regulation & EU-partner country FLEGT VPAs

To fight against illegal logging in VPA countries and related trade, the EU adopted the FLEGT Regulation (Council Regulation No 2173/2005), providing the legal framework for implementing EU-partner country FLEGT VPAs within the EU and laying down the procedure for accepting and verifying FLEGT licenses by EU Member States' competent authorities. Both instruments aim to promote legal timber production, trade, and consumption through market-creation for legally produced timber products on the EU single market (*markets pathway, Table 1*).

While EU-partner country FLEGT VPAs are initially voluntary, they become legally binding upon ratification by both partners. Partner countries must set up national timber legality licensing and assurance systems (TLAS) to comply with the EU FLEGT rules (Berning & Sotirov, 2023; Zeitlin & Overdevest, 2021) (*rules pathway*).

Effective VPA implementation requires VPA partner countries to agree on a national, multi-stakeholder definition of timber legality agreed upon by the government, private sector, and civil society based on norms of participatory deliberation (Overdevest & Zeitlin, 2014, 2018; Zeitlin & Overdevest, 2021). "Legally produced timber" under the FLEGT Regulation is defined as "timber products produced from domestic timber that was legally harvested or timber that was legally imported into a partner country in accordance with national laws determined by that partner country as set out in the Partnership Agreement" (Art. 2). The FLEGT Regulation and VPA rules thereby institutionalize a timber legality norm that respects producer countries' sovereignty and legality norms (Zeitlin & Overdevest, 2021) (*norms & discourses and rules pathways*).

Indonesia is the only country that has reached the full FLEGT VPA implementation stage. It has an operating TLAS system and has been issuing FLEGT licenses since 2016 (Overdevest & Zeitlin, 2018; Zeitlin & Overdevest, 2021). FLEGT licenses are issued by licensing authorities, entities authorized by Indonesia to issue and validate FLEGT licenses (Art. 2, 4). The EU-Indonesia FLEGT VPA's objective is twofold. First, the VPA seeks to provide a legal framework ensuring that specified timber imports from Indonesia have been legally produced, thereby promoting trade in timber products (*markets and rules pathways*). Second, the VPA seeks to provide the basis for dialogue and cooperation between the EU and Indonesia in implementing the agreement and enhancing forest law enforcement and governance in Indonesia (Art. 1) (*information & resources pathway*).

Under the EU-Indonesia FLEGT VPA, Indonesia must verify that only verified shipments are exported to the EU through its TLAS system (Art. 7). Indonesian timber is considered legal when the origin, production, processing, transport, and trade are compliant with all applicable laws and regulations in Indonesia (i.e., five legality standards) (Annex II). The EU can only accept Indonesian

shipments if they are covered by FLEGT licenses (Art. 3). Furthermore, EU Member States' competent authorities must verify the validity of FLEGT licenses of each shipment before releasing it on the EU market (Art. 7) (*rules pathway*).

Ghana, the Republic of the Congo, Cameroon, the Central African Republic, Liberia, and Viet Nam have reached a partial FLEGT VPA implementation stage (i.e., VPA agreement signed, ratified, and published in the Official Journal of the EU, ongoing development of TLAS) (see also section 9.4). Honduras and Guyana concluded negotiations with the EU. The Ivory Coast, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Gabon, Laos, Malaysia (put on hold), and Thailand embarked on formal bilateral negotiations (Carodenuto et al. 2024; Berning et al., 2023).

In return for VPA partner country supply-side timber legality assurance efforts, the EU – also negotiating on behalf of the EU Member States – committed to supporting VPA countries with capacity building and technical assistance to implement TLAS systems. The EU thereby seeks to support governance reforms and capacity building in VPA partner countries to contribute to sustainable forest management efforts (FLEGT Regulation, Recitals 2-4; Carodenuto et al. 2024). However, this cooperation with the EU may change in the future context of the EUDR and newly emerging Forest Partnerships (see sections 2.2 and 7.1) (Berning et al., 2023) (*information & resources pathway*).

In addition to this development-cooperation-based approach, the FLEGT Regulation's and VPA's theory of change relies on market-creating mechanisms (Table 1). For instance, Article 13 of the EU-Indonesia FLEGT VPA obliges the EU to promote a favorable position for specified timber products on the EU market. This includes 1) the recognition in public and private procurement policies and 2) the creation of a more favorable perception of FLEGT-licensed products on the Union market. Additionally, FLEGT-licensed timber and timber products had been granted a "green lane" market advantage under the EUTR, where FLEGT-licensed timber automatically fulfills the EUTR's due diligence requirements, facilitating its import to the EU (Carodenuto et al. 2024; Berning & Sotirov, 2023). The EUDR restricts this market pathway by no longer granting FLEGT-licensed products a green lane to the EU market (see section 2.2) (*rules and markets pathways*).

Under the EU-Indonesia FLEGT VPA, both parties must establish a Joint Implementation Committee (JIC) to establish the rules of procedure and meet on an annual basis (e.g., to review and monitor the VPA's implementation progress) (EU-Indonesia FLEGT VPA, Art. 14). The VPA also establishes a procedure to settle disputes (e.g., through prompt consultations and third-party mediation) (Art. 20) and the possibility to suspend the agreement (Art. 21) (*rules and norms & discourses pathways*).

3.2 EU-Mercosur free trade agreement (draft)

Negotiations for a free trade agreement between the EU and the four Mercosur countries – Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, and Uruguay – have been ongoing since 1995 (European Commission, 1996). In July 2019, the European Commission published a draft agreement summarizing the negotiation results

of the trade part of the EU-Mercosur Association Agreement from 28 June 2019 (European Commission, 2019). Since then, negotiations paused during the presidency of Bolsonaro in Brazil from 2019 to 2022 (Sotirov et al., 2022) and picked up again during the Lula presidency in Brazil in 2023 (Reuters, 2023). The EU presented Mercosur with an addendum outlining several environmental safeguards to address reservations by many EU Member States (European Commission, 2023a; b; Reuters, 2023). While the negotiation and adoption of the agreement are voluntary, it will become legally binding upon ratification by both partners (Berning et al., 2023b) (*rules pathway*).

The overarching policy goal of the draft agreement is to liberalize trade in goods by facilitating trade flows between the EU and Mercosur (e.g., through tariff liberalization and duty eliminations). This includes market access for agricultural goods. Under the draft, the EU agreed to liberalize agricultural imports such as beef, poultry, pigmeat, and sugar. Mercosur would also agree to liberalize key products of EU export interest (e.g., wine, olive oil, and fresh fruits) and to offer EU industries access to cheaper high-quality raw materials such as soybean products for animal feed (Chapter 1) (*markets pathway, Table 1*).

The Trade and Sustainable Development (TSD) chapter seeks to ensure that increased trade does not result in increased environmental degradation or undermining labor conditions and instead contributes to promoting sustainable development (Chapter 14). Upon adoption, the trade agreement would institutionalize normative assumptions about win-win synergies between economic, social, and environmental policy goals (cf. Berning & Sotirov, 2024; Vos, 2007) (*norms & discourses pathway*).

Under the TSD chapter, both parties agree to respect socio-environmental standards, including International Labour Organization Conventions (i.e., on forced and child labor, non-discrimination at work, freedom of association and right to collective bargaining), multilateral environmental agreements such as the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), committing to implement the Paris Agreement effectively, and promoting responsible business conduct in line with the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) Guidelines or UN Guiding Principles of Business and Human Rights. The agreement also includes an in-built mechanism for civil-society consultation. The TSD chapter further includes commitments regarding sustainable forest management and safeguards initiatives on sustainable agriculture, including EU private sector actions on zero deforestation supply chains and producer-led initiatives such as the Brazilian Amazon soy moratorium (Chapter 14). The EU's 2023 addition to the trade deal includes a more comprehensive range of international commitments (e.g., 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, UN Declaration on Rights of Indigenous Peoples) and specific socio-environmental commitments concerning environmental and labor protection, climate change, biological diversity, forests, labor rights, cooperation, human rights, civil society, as well as monitoring and review processes (European Commission, 2023a).

The 2019 draft agreement includes a set of rules for both parties to adhere to (e.g., rules of origin, customs, trade facilitation, trade remedy, competition, subsidy, and WTO rules) while maintaining the Parties' right to regulate (e.g.,

the provision of public services) (*rules pathway*). The agreement also lists a range of dialogue-creating measures (e.g., cooperation in international fora) (*norms and discourses pathway*) and foresees creating access to government procurement markets (i.e., goods, services, and works purchased by public entities) (*markets pathway*) (Chapters 2-16). The agreement would also establish dispute settlement mechanisms to resolve disputes between the Parties in relation to interpreting, applying, complying, and enforcing the agreement (e.g., consultations, the establishment of an arbitration panel) (Chapter 17) (*rules pathway*).

Under the agreement, both parties would also commit to cooperate through dialogues and information exchanges to strengthen mutual confidence and improve common understanding on various issues. These include issues around 1) raising animal welfare, 2) applying agricultural biotechnology, 3) antimicrobial resistance, and 4) scientific matters related to food safety, animal, and plant health (Chapter 6) (*information & resources pathway*).

4. Transnational private regulation

4.1 Certification - the example of FSC

Certification schemes are prominent examples of transnational private regulation in the social-environmental realm. They are described as innovative nonstate market-driven governance mechanisms (Cashore, 2002), working primarily without state regulation (Abbott & Snidal, 2021). Non-state actors are decisive in designing and implementing sustainability standards for FERCs. Albeit voluntary for companies to comply, this governance mechanism is legally binding under private law, as it implies contracts between private organizations along the supply chain (see private law definition under Methods) (*rules pathway*).

After a failed intergovernmental attempt to agree on a legally binding global forest convention during the 1990s, the first private regulations to certify sustainable forest management practices and set chain of custody standards were the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) multistakeholder certification – managed by NGOs, civil society organizations (CSOs), companies, and producers – and the competing industry-led Program for the Endorsement of Forest Certification (PEFC) (Sotirov et al., 2020; Abbott & Snidal, 2021). In the agricultural sector, similar NGO and industry regulations set sustainability standards for agricultural commodities (e.g., coffee, soy, palm oil) and cattle/beef production and supply chains. Central schemes include the NGO-led Rainforest Alliance and competing industry-led 4C coffee certification schemes (Lambin et al., 2018). Key multistakeholder certification schemes include the Roundtable on Sustainable Palm Oil (RSPO) and Round Table on Responsible Soy (RTRS). The Global Roundtable on Sustainable Beef (GRSB) is a multistakeholder certification scheme additionally involving regulatory authorities and governmental agencies as consulting members (Abbott & Snidal, 2021; Garrett et al., 2019; Lambin et al., 2018; Berning & Sotirov, 2023).

The FSC is a leading FRC certification system with decades-long and global

adherence in the forest sector (Basso et al., 2018; Da Silva et al., 2019; Susilawati & Kanowski, 2021). It was founded in 1993 in Mexico as a voluntary certification system for sustainable forestry. At the core of its business is the purpose of “nurturing responsible forestry so forests and people can thrive,” institutionalizing the norm of forest protection, yet in balance with socio-economic development goals (*norms & discourses pathway*).

Its main goals are the promotion of environmentally sound, socially beneficial, and economically viable management of the world’s forests (*norms & discourses pathway*). It has the most extensive global certified supply chain network, connecting markets and sustainable forestry, including over 200 million hectares of forest managed following FSC standards (e.g., considering environmental and biodiversity impacts, workers' rights, avoiding over-consumption and over-harvesting, tenure use rights, indigenous peoples' rights, management plans). The FSC’s governance comprises a global network of members, staff, certificate holders, promotional license holders, and responsible consumers. Following this multi-stakeholder system, there is an elected board and a general assembly. FSC certifies forest management for environmental-social standards, but also the chain of custody, verifying that forest-based materials produced according to their standards “are credibly used along the product’s path from the forest to becoming finished goods” (FSC, 2023) (*rules pathway*).

The FSC implements its work through the core concept of collaboration between NGOs, businesses, and consumers and increasingly uses research and technology to achieve its best standards and monitoring (*information & resources pathway*). As a non-state market-driven governance mechanism, its objective is only achieved if both sides of the supply chain (producers and consumers) agree, comply, and buy their sustainability standards. Therefore, these mechanisms have frequently appeared due to the pressure of civil society in naming and shaming companies on their social and environmental standards (*norms & discourses pathway*) (Sotirov et al., 2020). In terms of its intervention logic, it primarily works through a market incentive logic by incentivizing producers and other value chain actors to obtain the certification in the promise of accessing a wider market, price premiums for certified goods, preferential treatment by buyers, and exposure to new clients (van der Ven & Cashore, 2018). Moreover, the naming and shaming campaigns themselves have a market intervention logic since they intend to affect the company’s image, which tends to result in economic losses (e.g., profit loss, share price drop) (*markets pathway, Table 1*).

5. (Sub-)national private regulation

5.1 Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium

The Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium is a legally binding private agreement signed in 2006 between companies, civil society, and, from 2008 onwards, the public sector (see private law definition under Methods) (*rules pathway*). While companies can voluntarily decide to adhere to the moratorium, sourcing requirements from signatory businesses are legally binding for upstream suppliers and verified by third-party auditors. In the early 2000s, non-state actors (e.g., NGOs) were prominent in advocating for the halt of deforestation

driven by soy commodity trade (Greenpeace, 2006). The Moratorium institutionalized a zero deforestation norm by committing to the goal of ensuring zero deforestation of soy sourced from the Amazon region (Gibbs et al., 2015). Pressured by NGO advocacy and driven by reputational concerns, major soybean traders (e.g., members of the Brazilian Association of Vegetable Oil Industries (ABIOVE) and the National Association of Grain Exporters (ANEC)) agreed to not sell, purchase, or finance soy from areas deforested in the Amazon biome after July 2008. The moratorium was renewed every two years and became indefinite in 2016 (Inakake de Souza et al., 2016) (*norms & discourses pathway*).

The Moratorium's governance is done through its multi-stakeholder Soy Working Group, which includes the private sector, the civil society, and the state. Its governance and enforcement highly depend on a monitoring process that includes satellite data from the National Institute for Space Research's (INPE's) Amazon Deforestation Monitoring Project (PRODES) project and the state instrument of the Rural Environmental Registry (CAR) (*information & resources pathway*).

This monitoring results in a list of farmers producing soy in deforested land. As a strong market disincentive, companies signatory to the agreement are obliged to comply by not buying soybeans from sanctioned farmers in order to meet the Moratorium's deforestation standard. Albeit designed following normative pressure, the Brazilian Amazon Soy Moratorium primarily relies on direct economic sanctions on farmers that deforest for soy production. Third-party auditors identify non-compliant companies, and these receive recommendations for improvement (*markets pathway, Table 1*). As a means of transparency, auditing reports are available for all signatories and the Soy Working Group (Inakake de Souza et al., 2016).

6. Industry self-regulation

6.1 Consumer Goods Forum's Forest Positive Coalition of Action

The Consumer Goods Forum (CGF) dates back to 1953. In its current form, it was officially founded in December 2009 in Paris. It is an industry-led collaborative and non-profit organization that brings together more than 400 Chief Executive Officers (CEOs) and senior management members from global manufacturing, retailing, and service-providing companies. These operate in over 100 countries and collectively generate a total of EUR 3.5 trillion in sales. Their headquarter is in Paris, with regional offices in Tokyo, Washington D.C., Bogota, and Shanghai. They aim to 1) optimize global value chains for consumers and strengthen the performance of the Consumer Goods Industry, 2) promote collaboration on non-competitive matters that support the delivery of better goods and services to consumers in a more efficient and sustainable model, 3) provide a global forum for chief executives of member companies to exchange ideas and information on future trends, current techniques and best practices in the industry worldwide, and 4) improve professional standards and company performance in the service of the consumer. Their mission is to drive positive change and help address key challenges impacting the industry, including environmental and social sustainability, health, food safety, and product data accuracy, doing so for the benefit of both people and the planet,

as well as their businesses (The Consumer Goods Forum, 2022) (*markets and information & resources pathways*).

As the CGF's strategy was revisited together with the failed efforts to reach the 2010 commitment of achieving zero-net deforestation by 2020, the Forest Positive Coalition of Action was established in 2020. It is a CEO-led initiative representing 20 CGF member companies committed to leveraging collective action and accelerating systemic efforts to remove deforestation, forest degradation, and conversion from key commodity supply chains. The Forest Positive Coalition of Action is a transnational, non-legally binding governance mechanism. Since its efforts in 2010, the Coalition stated to have noticed that solely focusing on individual supply chains and relying on certification will not drive the full-sector transformation needed to end deforestation (Forest Positive Coalition of Action, 2021).

Driven by global zero deforestation norms, carried and advocated for by non-state actors in academia, civil society, and the private sector (Neeff & Linhares-Juvenal, 2017; Austin et al., 2021), the coalition seeks to achieve four deforestation-related goals: 1) accelerate efforts to remove commodity-driven deforestation from their supply chains, 2) set higher expectations for suppliers and traders to act across their entire supply base, 3) drive transformational change in key commodity landscapes, and 4) define agreed measurable outcomes to be tracked and reported individually and collectively by all members (*norms & discourses pathway*).

These goals are achieved by establishing new market practices, especially through market incentives to access new markets, which would be enabled by the collaboration and exchange of information between CGF members. Concrete achieved actions include commodity-specific roadmaps for palm oil, soy, paper, pulp and fiber-based packaging, and beef (The Consumer Goods Forum, 2022) (*markets and information & resources pathways*).

The Coalition's implementation is monitored by Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) outlined in each commodity roadmap. Proforest and the Tropical Forest Alliance provide technical support in developing and monitoring the KPIs. The CGF's statute is publicly available and includes the association's governance mechanisms to enhance accountability and transparency. Furthermore, the Forest Positive Coalition publicly reports on its achievements and KPIs, although not at an annual or consistent rate. Membership in the CGF and the Forest Positive Coalition is voluntary, and members agree to follow soft rules by signing the statute. Non-compliance is not sanctionable with hard penalties (e.g., fines) (*rules pathway*).

7. Transnational biodiversity & and biomass-related strategies & initiatives

7.1 Forest Partnerships

At the COP 27 UN Climate Change Conference, the Commission President signed Forest Partnership Memoranda of Understanding with five countries (i.e., Guyana, Mongolia, the Republic of Congo, Uganda, and Zambia) as a contribution to the external action-oriented dimension of the EU Green Deal after their first announcement at the UN Climate Change Conference COP26 in

Glasgow (European Commission, 2022a).

The stated policy goal is to establish a holistic cooperation framework to jointly reverse deforestation in supported countries, thereby enhancing climate and biodiversity protection. While every Forest Partnership is tailored to the specific situation and signatory country, the EU seeks political commitments from both partners to 1) ensure sustainable forest management by improving forest governance and enhancing the business environment, 2) generate an economic transformation by stimulating the forest bio-economy, 3) reduce deforestation and forest degradation, and 4) identify ways to facilitate production of and trade in legal and sustainable forest products (European Commission, 2022a). Upon their signature, Forest Partnerships will institutionalize the norm to fight deforestation and forest degradation outside the EU while contributing to supply-side socio-economic development and ensuring the production of legal and sustainable forest products for the EU market (*norms & discourses pathway*). Forest Partnerships are soft laws due to their non-legally binding nature (*rules pathway*).

Compared to FLEGT VPAs, Forest Partnerships' theory of change relies more on a development-cooperation-based logic without trade-related market incentives (*information & resources pathway, Table 1*). Table 2 provides an overview of Forest Partnerships' key work streams and investment objectives, as outlined in the individual fact sheets. Notably, expected land use policy and governance reforms are coupled with a strong focus on market-creating investments (e.g., loans, lifted barriers to investments) (*markets pathway*).

Table 2: Fact sheet overview of EU-partner country Forest Partnership agreements (European Commission, 2022b).

Country	Key work streams of the Forest Partnership	Forest Partnership investment
Guyana	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improved governance and regulations in favor of forest sector development ● Sustainable forest management and forest-based value chains ● Ecosystem services based on forest conservation ● Maintain a low rate of deforestation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Forest carbon credits ● Support to state agencies ● Guarantees for loans and private sector ● Private sector investments in wood production ● Blended finance
Uganda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improved governance and sustainable use and management of forests ● Forest-based value chains covering wood and non-wood forest products ● Address deforestation and forest degradation ● Conservation and restoration of natural forest and ecosystem corridors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Lifting barriers to investments ● Enable smallholders' access to finance ● Support in land tenure, land use planning, and deforestation-free agriculture
Zambia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Good governance environment: Forest policy, governance, and management systems ● Economic transformation and job creation: Improved value chains for forest products and services ● Environmental sustainability: A value to protect ● Human and social development: Skills training, research and outreach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Stimulate private sector initiatives ● Carbon markets and result-based payments ● Support bankable forest-related projects ● Access to finance for micro, small, and medium enterprises

Country	Key work streams of the Forest Partnership	Forest Partnership investment
Mongolia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improved governance, sustainable use, and management of forests ● Sustainable forest management and forest-based value chains ● Reduction of deforestation and forest degradation ● Conservation and restoration of Natural Forest 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Removing barriers to investments ● Outgrower schemes with small holders ● Support bankable forest-related projects ● Investments in the forest-value chains
Republic of Congo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improved governance (sustainable management of forests, peatlands, and their carbon stocks) ● Promotion of a sustainable forest economy and wood processing at the national level ● Promotion of deforestation-free agriculture ● Preservation of biodiversity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Promoting investment, particularly in wood processing capacity ● Removing obstacles to investment development ● Improving the capacity of local financial institutions ● Supporting bankable forestry projects

8. Supranational biodiversity and biomass-related strategies & initiatives

8.1 Central African Economic and Monetary Community log export ban

A log export ban in the Congo Basin region is a decision that has been announced by the CEMAC, consisting of Cameroon, the Central African Republic, the Republic of the Congo, Gabon, Equatorial Guinea, and Chad. Under the decision, these countries commit to banning the export of raw, unprocessed logs from their territories. This aims to regulate and control the export of logs from the Congo Basin region, promote the local transformation of wood, and increase the forestry sector's contribution to the countries' Gross Domestic Product. The decision is non-legally binding and only becomes legally binding to a country when it adopts the decision's measures into its domestic legal framework. Cameroon, for example, has not yet done so, while in Gabon, there have been legally binding measures to ban the export of raw logs in place since 2010. The decision was first made in 2020 (to begin in 2022), but it has been postponed twice, in 2021 (to begin in 2023) and 2023 (to begin in 2025) (*rules pathway, Table 1*).

The core of the decision is for the CEMAC countries to forbid the export of raw logs and to process their entire wood production within their territories. The countries are to create special economic zones for primary, secondary, and tertiary wood processing industries to address the current deficit of processing capacities. Furthermore, the decision entails the creation of harmonized forestry taxation guidelines in the CEMAC region to be incorporated into national legislation. Enforcement of the log export ban decision lies within national authorities after the decision has been adopted into domestic legal frameworks (*rules pathway*).

In this way, the CEMAC log export ban decision promotes a norm of forestry sector industrialization and economic development in the Congo Basin region, as the development of the timber industries is supposed to contribute to local job creation and Gross Domestic Product growth. This is in opposition to exporting low-value timber products, to which value is added only abroad. This is also directly linked to increased government revenues by capturing more value from timber resources within the borders of the CEMAC countries. The CEMAC State actors strongly advocate for these narratives to gain support for the decision (*norms & discourses pathway*). Moreover, through the hard rules applied, the decision incentivizes market actors for industry development, value addition, and job creation within the countries, as logs are to be processed into (semi-)finished products (*markets and rules pathways*).

The decision also contains a provision for creating a regional committee for the sustainable industrialization of the timber sector in the Congo Basin (*information & resources pathway*).

8.2 Belém Declaration

In August 2023 the Leaders of State Parties to the Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization (ACTO) met in the city of Belém do Pará, Brazil, and agreed on the Belém Declaration, a supranational non-legally binding instrument (Berning et al., 2023b). State parties to the ACTO include Brazil, Bolivia, Colombia, Ecuador, Guyana, Peru, Suriname, and Venezuela (ACTO, 2023). The Belém Declaration’s goal is to combine the efforts of the 8 Amazon Governments to advance a new common sustainability agenda for the Amazon. This agenda is to be implemented through 113 cross-cutting objectives. These objectives address the broader topics of 1) institutional strengthening of ACTO, governance of the Amazon in different levels, 2) science, education, and innovation: knowledge and entrepreneurship in the Amazon, 3) monitoring and cooperation in water resources management, 4) climate change, 5) protection of forests, Amazon coastal zones, vulnerable ecosystems, and biodiversity, 6) social protection, 7) human rights and social participation, among many others.

The Declaration was adopted right after the EUDRs’ adoption (see section 2.2) as a regional counter-argument. The Declaration condemns unilateral trade measures based on normative environmental requirements, which constitute trade barriers and primarily affect smallholder farmers in developing countries and the pursuit of sustainable development in the Amazon (Recital). It also strengthens the role of ACTO as the only intergovernmental coordination body for the eight Amazon countries due to its institutionality, its extensive knowledge of the region, and the relevant experience of its Permanent Secretariat in coordinating dialogue and implementing development cooperation initiatives in the region (Recital) (*norms & discourses pathway, Table 1*).

The Declaration also highlights developed countries’ obligation to provide and mobilize funds and support developing countries in dealing with environmental and social issues in the region (e.g., climate change, biodiversity conservation) (Recital and Objective 35). Moreover, on financing and engaging the private sector for its accomplishment, they indicated their willingness to work with development banks and announced the formation of the Green Coalition. This Coalition promotes environmental-social financial solutions for the region through financial support to public and private projects to support “sustainable, inclusive economic alternatives, with local generation of employment and income opportunities, especially for low-income families” (Objective 82) (*markets pathway*).

As a non-legally binding instrument, non-compliance cannot be sanctioned through legal procedures. Compliance primarily relies on adherence to soft normative principles. These include the establishment of working groups, mechanisms, forums, and actions to be taken. Furthermore, compliance relies on the adherence to agreed normative principles under Objective 1 (e.g., indigenous peoples’ and local communities’ rights, human rights, gender equality, intercultural and intergenerational approach, and the sovereignty of the states) (*rules and norms & discourses pathways*). Objective 2 also emphasizes the strengthening of cooperation between the Amazon governments to improve national capacities of State Parties through an exchange of good practices, knowledge, and public policies, South-South cooperation, and mobilization of international cooperation resources. The Declaration primarily relies on a development-cooperation-based approach for

its achievement (Recital, Objectives 7, 11, 25, 32, 54, 75) (*information & resources pathway, Table 1*).

9. National biodiversity and biomass-related public policies

9.1 Brazil: Forest Code

The Native Vegetation Protection Law - 12.651/2012

The Brazilian Forest Code (Law 12.651/2012) was first established in 1934 and has since been amended several times (i.e., in 1965, 1981, 1989, 1996, 2001, and 2006). The latest 2012 amendment was particularly supported by the agricultural and livestock grazing defenders in the congress, usually called the “ruralists” (Santos Filho et al., 2015). The Forest Code is a national law, thus a legally binding instrument, that establishes general rules on protecting vegetation and preserving areas in national territory. It also regulates the supply of forest raw materials, the origin of forest products, and the prevention of forest fires. It obliges landowners to preserve a minimum of 20% of native vegetation cover in their property. These obligations are higher in the Cerrado “transitional area”, which includes the Legal Amazon (35%) and in the Amazon (80%) (Art. 12) (*rules pathway, Table 1*).

Furthermore, the Forest Code relies on economic and financial instruments to achieve its objectives. These include credit lines, tax reductions, and tradeable certificates (Art. 1) (*markets pathway*).

The Forest Code’s principles follow national sustainable development norms and objectives. It reinforces Brazil’s sovereign commitment to protect its forests while stating that forests are assets of common interest to all the country’s inhabitants. For instance, its principles affirm the important role of agriculture and forests in the country’s economic growth by providing global food and bioenergy markets (*norms & discourses pathway*) (Art. 1, 2).

Additionally, Article 41 stipulates that the state should create support programs and incentives for environmental conservation, as well as for the adoption of technologies and good practices that reconcile agricultural and forestry productivity with a reduction in environmental impacts. These include compensation for conservation measures, agricultural credits, credit lines to support initiatives for the voluntary preservation of native vegetation, and deduction from the owner’s income tax base, among others (*markets pathway*).

The Forest Code’s compliance also relies on the implementation of existing information provisions and systems monitored by the state (e.g., CAR, SISNAMA (National Environment System)) (*information & resources pathway*). To ensure compliance, the use and exploitation of vegetation and actions or omissions contrary to the provisions of this law are considered illegal and can be enforced through criminal sanctions (Art. 2) (*rules pathway, Table 1*).

9.2 Brazil: Environmental Crimes Law

Law No. 9.605/1998

In 1998, the Brazilian Environmental Crimes Law (9.605/1998) was passed,

and it has been in force since then. The law institutionalizes environmental protection as a norm and duty of the state (*norms & discourses, rules pathway*).

It is a national law, thus a legally binding instrument, that defines environmental crimes as aggressions against the environment and its components (i.e., flora, fauna, natural resources, cultural heritage) that go beyond the limits established by law; or conduct that ignores legally established environmental standards, even if no damage is caused to the environment (Chapter 5). Such crimes can be sanctioned with criminal and administrative penalties, including imprisonment (i.e., from three months to six years) and fines (i.e., described as “pena” (penalty) under each Article) (*rules pathway, Table 1*).

Furthermore, Chapter 7 highlights the importance of international cooperation for the preservation of the environment by stating that the Brazilian government – under its national sovereignty – should cooperate with other countries on matters related to the environment. International cooperation should be reciprocal with a form of communications system (*information & resources pathway*).

Besides relying on penalties, such as fines as market disincentives, the law does not institutionalize additional market-correcting mechanisms to achieve its objectives (*markets and rules pathways*).

9.3 Cameroon: Forestry Law

Law 94/01 of 20 January 1994 laying down regulations for forestry, wildlife, and fisheries

The Cameroon Forestry Law was adopted in 1994 and entered into force in 1995. Its implementation is governed by Decree No. 95/531 of August 23, 1995, setting out the application of the forestry regime and other subsequent decrees. The revision of the law has been in process since 2008. Being part of the Cameroon domestic legal framework, it is a national, legally binding instrument aimed at influencing the domestic forestry domain. The overall objectives of the law are to ensure integrated management and sustainable use and conservation of forest resources and ecosystems, increase revenues from forests for economic development, and allow local communities and populations to exploit forest resources (Ekoko, 2000) (*rules pathway, Table 1*).

The law sets and defines access rights to and requirements for the exploitation and management of forest resources, including management planning procedures and principles (Part III), as well as financial and fiscal provisions (Part IV) (*rules pathway*). Provisions on the transformation of timber products, such as that 70% of the total production of logs shall be processed by the local industry within five years of the enactment of the law, incentivize the development of wood processing capacities in the country (Part III) (*markets pathway*). For the first time in Cameroon, local communities can also obtain forestry exploitation rights under the law through community forestry. The elaboration of a management plan – meant to ensure sustainable forest management – approved by the competent forest administration is, in most cases, a prerequisite for the exploitation of forest products. The law also

specifies enforcement and prosecution procedures, offenses, and penalties (e.g., fines, imprisonment) (Part VI) (*rules pathway*).

Considering the importance given to sustainable forest management planning under the law, the law institutionalizes sustainable forest management as an overall forestry standard to balance production and conservation efforts in Cameroon. With the introduction of community forestry, the law also promotes the idea of decentralized forestry through local communities and local-level forest use and management rights. However, the law focuses on regulating the export-oriented industrial forestry sector and largely neglects the domestic timber market (*norms & discourses and rules pathways*).

The law contains no explicit provisions for information and/or resource transfer.

9.4 Cameroon: FLEGT-VPA

The FLEGT-VPA (see also section 3.1 for a more general perspective) between the EU and Cameroon was signed in 2010 and adopted (ratified) in 2011. It is a trade agreement that provides a legal framework for ensuring that timber and timber products exported from Cameroon to the EU are legally produced or acquired. As such, it is aimed at fighting illegal logging in Cameroon to ensure legal Cameroon-EU timber and timber product supply chains. The VPA was voluntarily negotiated between the two parties but became legally binding with its ratification. In this way, it is a part of the EU and Cameroon legal frameworks, and its design was co-determined by both parties to the agreement. However, it is mainly aimed at influencing the Cameroonian timber sector, and its implementation is prescribed to happen through Cameroonian national tools, like the second-generation Computerized Forest Information Management System (SIGIF II) (see below). The underlying logic of the EU-Cameroon VPA is to provide economic incentives for improved EU market access, which is meant to help foster strengthened forest law enforcement and governance in Cameroon (*markets pathway, Table 1*).

In this vein, the VPA promotes a norm of legality in Cameroon's timber sector. This comprises an understanding of what is legal and how legality is enforced, as detailed below. A focus on national legality – rather than sustainability, for example – was regarded as an agreeable joint goal to the VPA parties, as it can be seen as respecting the national sovereignty of the producing country (Overdevest & Zeitlin, 2018) (see also section 3.1). Beyond timber legality, the VPA highlights improved governance in the timber sector, including transparency and strengthened participation in policy design and implementation of all stakeholders, like state actors, NGOs, and indigenous peoples (see, for example, the national monitoring committee below) (*norms & discourses pathway*).

The VPA introduces a FLEGT Licensing scheme between the EU and Cameroon, requiring the implementation of an independent audit to ensure the performance and efficiency of the FLEGT licensing process. As a legally binding agreement, the VPA stipulates in a set of legality matrices how it defines legal timber and timber products (Article 8 and Annex II). The agreement also requires the development of a Legality Verification System (LVS) (also known as TLAS) by the forest administration, operationalized through SIGIF II, a

national monitoring tool for forestry activities (Article 9 and Annex III). The LVS is meant to verify the legality and upstream traceability of specified forest products. Moreover, the VPA contains specific provisions on transparency and information publishing (Article 21 and Annex VII) and the participation of stakeholders in implementing the agreement (Article 16 and Annexes III-A, III-B, and X). Similar to the EU-Indonesia VPA (see section 3.1), the EU-Cameroon VPA also sets institutional arrangements for its implementation and monitoring, such as a Joint Implementation Council and a Joint Monitoring Committee (Article 19), and defines dispute settlement procedures (Article 24) and allows for suspension of the agreement (Article 25) (*rules pathway*).

Importantly, the VPA offers a market incentive as Cameroonian timber products accompanied by a FLEGT license may enter the EU market directly without further restrictions by the EUTR (i.e., green lane market advantage). Similar to the EU-Indonesia VPA (see section 3.1), the agreement further specifies that access to the EU market shall be accompanied by promotional campaigns for timber and timber products (Article 18). It also recognizes FSC and Origine et Légalité des Bois (OLB) private sustainability certification and legality verification schemes in the development of the legality matrices (Annex II) (*markets pathway*).

The VPA also mandates exchanges of information in relation to the functioning of the FLEGT scheme, whereby the parties “undertake to inform one another immediately of any concerns they may have regarding potential cases of fraud associated with the use or issue of the FLEGT licences” (Article 12). The agreement also allows for various supporting measures for different areas where there is a need for additional technical and financial resources in order to implement the VPA (Article 15 and Annex X). These are related to financing mechanisms and other supporting measures, such as capacity building, strengthening the national control system, or acquiring equipment and logistical tools (*information & resources pathway*).

9.5 Gabon: Forest Code

Law 016/01 of December 31, 2001 establishing the Forest Code in the Gabonese Republic

The current Forest Code was adopted in Gabon in 2001. As such, it is a legally binding instrument and part of the national legal framework. A number of laws, decrees, ordinances, and orders have been passed in various fields to ensure its implementation (e.g., the National Technical Guide for Forest Management, adopted in 2004). The law aims to ensure sustainable management of forests and by-products from industrial and artisanal logging, conserve and protect biodiversity, drive further industrialization of the timber industry, and involve local populations in the sustainable management of natural resources (*rules pathway, Table 1*).

In the context of forest exploitation, the law defines the crucial role of forest management plans and planning as necessary for performing forestry operations – meant as a tool to ensure sustainable forest management (Articles 17, 20-22, and 30). Hereby, it sets the conditions for businesses related to accessing forest resources, forest inventory and management, logging, and marketing of forest products (e.g., Articles 233-243) (*rules pathway*). An essential element is also the inclusion of hard rules that mandate and stimulate

market-creating measures on the industrialization of the timber industry (Articles 220-232). For example, Article 227 states that the transformation rate of local production must evolve to reach 75% during the decade following the promulgation of the law (*markets pathway*). As an essential element of the law, a set of Articles (156-162) define local community exploitation rights for timber products under community forests. Articles 262-284 also stipulate the state's prerogative for law monitoring and enforcement, including defining sanctions for offenses and cases of non-compliance (*rules pathway*).

The law institutionalizes a set of norms and standards through these hard rules. A key standard amongst these is sustainable forest management, which is meant to cover Gabonese forests and forestry activities via the general and technical provisions in the law. In addition, the law seeks to institutionalize a norm of a developed, high-quality local forest industry consisting of larger and smaller national businesses, which in turn contributes to the country's economic development, such as job creation and Gross Domestic Product growth. Moreover, the possibility for local communities to manage and commercially benefit from the forests from which they derive their livelihood has been introduced through the institutionalization of decentralized forestry in the form of community forests (*norms & discourses and rules pathways*).

Provisions particular to information/resources transfer are not included in the law.

9.6 Gabon: Mandatory FSC certification

In 2018, Gabon announced that all its forest concessions would need to become FSC-certified by 2022 or otherwise cease their operations. This announcement was made in the form of a Presidential Declaration during the former president's visit to the Mevang sawmill of Rougier Gabon. The declaration is non-legally binding, yet it has carried a quasi-legal influence and is further in the process of becoming incorporated into the Gabonese legal framework.

This governance mechanism generally institutionalizes sustainable forest management standards (as defined by FSC) in Gabon, highlighting environmentally sound, socially beneficial, and economically viable forest management. From the state's perspective, it also advocates for improving the quality, attractiveness, and competitiveness of Gabonese forest products on international markets and access of the products to the markets – which would be the expected benefits of FSC certification. It sets a norm for a professional, internationally competitive, and sustainable Gabonese forestry sector (*norms & discourses pathway*).

The main logic behind making FSC certification mandatory in Gabon essentially relies on a combination of domestic rules and transnational private regulation. On the one hand, timber businesses are to become FSC certified, which should provide them market incentives, such as price premiums or preferential access to markets, but also improve the quality and sustainability of forestry operations (see also section 4.1). In doing this, the government also believes that FSC-certifying the country's whole forestry private sector will be beneficial to the sector and to economic development. On the other hand, by making the

obtainment of FSC certification for forest concessionaires mandatory – while adopting FSC certification by default is voluntary for a business – the government leverages its rule setting and enforcement power (e.g., see section 9.1), as it will withdraw licenses to operate from forestry businesses not becoming FSC certified (*rules and markets pathways, Table 1*).

The declaration contains a short note on the government to support the forestry businesses towards FSC certification to facilitate complete certification uptake in Gabon. However, the details remain unclear (*information & resources pathway*).

10. (Sub-)national biodiversity and biomass-related strategies & initiatives

10.1 Interstate Consortium for the Sustainable Development of the Legal Amazon

The Interstate Consortium for the Sustainable Development of the Legal Amazon was established in 2019 by the nine Amazonian states: Acre, Amapá, Amazonas, Mato Grosso, Maranhão, Pará, Rondônia, Roraima, and Tocantins. It is an autark public association that integrates the indirect administration of all Brazilian federal member states. Its goal is to accelerate the sustainable development of the Legal Amazon in an integrated and cooperative way, considering regional opportunities and challenges. Its vision is to be a global reference in articulation, strategy, and governance to transform the Legal Amazon into a competitive, integrated, and sustainable region by 2030. Its first phase has an 11-year implementation period (2019-2030). The strategy includes the development of governance, indicators, and monitoring mechanisms and is based on four strategic axes: 1) green economy, competitiveness, and innovation; 2) regional integration; 3) territorial and environmental governance; and 4) management, governance and priority public services, including specific objectives and priority projects (Consórcio Interestadual Amazônia Legal, 2019).

Local governments established and designed it to institutionalize sustainable development strategies for the region. This includes projects related to a green economy and environmental governance (Section 1) (*norms & discourses pathway*). Furthermore, all nine state governments commit to cooperating and collaborating by exchanging information and converging their policies to achieve sustainable development goals (Sections 1 & 7) (*information & resources pathway*). The strategy also encourages working with other stakeholders and engaging in private-public initiatives. This includes working with development banks, funds, and innovative forms of financing (Section 7) (*markets pathway*).

As a non-legally binding Brazilian sub-national governance strategy, non-compliance cannot be sanctioned through legal procedures. Compliance primarily relies on normative adherence to soft rules (*rules and norms & discourses pathways, Table 1*).

Another key jurisdictional approach to regulate FERCs in Brazil is the “Produce, Conserve, Include” (Produzir, Conservar, Incluir) strategy of the federal state Mato Grosso, founded in 2015. It aims to raise funds for the state of Mato Grosso while seeking to expand and increase the efficiency of agricultural and

forestry production (*markets pathway*). Objectives also include conserving the remaining native vegetation, restoring environmental liabilities, and the socio-economic inclusion of family farming while reducing emissions and carbon sequestration of 6 GTonCO₂ by controlling deforestation and developing a low-carbon economy (*norms & discourses pathway*). Ambitious in its goal, it was designed in a multi-stakeholder approach. Since 2019, it has entered a second phase, whereby the strategy is governed by a formalized Institute, which includes all actors of society (Estado do Mato Grosso, 2021).

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

What are the designed and expected theories of change of key public policies and private governance mechanisms regulating legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk commodity supply chains? What are their main intervention logics, and how do they interact?

Overall, we identified a dominant intervention logic or theory of change such as (1.) rules or (2.) norms & discourses or (3.) markets or (4.) information & resources within each public policy and private governance mechanism. At the same time, the dominant intervention logics of most public and private instruments are (1.) rules ("I") and/or (3.) markets ("E"). However, the intervention logics of the analyzed public and private regulation often compete among each other. This can explain policy (in-)effectiveness of the variety of all forest related regulations as a positive transformative impact would strongly rely on successfully implementing designed synergies and avoid contradictions with other intervention logics within the same instrument or other instruments.

This report empirically shows that public and private regulations at the international level and across the EU, Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon regulating forest and ecosystem-risk commodity supply chains rely on a combination of legally binding and non-binding intervention logics.

First, a dominant intervention logic could be identified within each policy and governance mechanism (i.e., rules vs. norms & discourses vs. markets vs. information & resources). Second, the dominant intervention logic within each instrument relies on designed synergies with other intervention logics within the same instrument or other instruments (Table 1).

For legally binding instruments under public law this includes the institutionalization of norms and discourses (e.g., fight against climate change, deforestation, forest degradation, and human rights violations), market incentives (e.g., green lane for FLEGT-licensed timber under the EUTR, recognition of private FERC certification systems), market disincentives (e.g., prohibitions, due diligence obligations), and information and resource mechanisms (e.g., mandatory cooperation with partner countries under the EUDR) in hard laws with monitoring (e.g., controls, checks) and enforcement mechanisms (e.g., sanctions, penalties).

The EUTR, EUDR, CEMAC log export ban (once adopted in national law), Brazil Forest Code, Brazil Environmental Crime Law, Cameroon Forestry Law, and

Gabon Forest Code are hard laws primarily relying on regulatory intervention logics (*rules pathway*) supported by non-regulatory intervention logics (i.e., norms & discourses, markets, information & resources). The FLEGT Regulation and EU-partner country FLEGT VPAs, EU-Mercosur free trade agreement (draft), and Gabon mandatory FSC certification institutionalize market incentives (*markets pathway*) in hard public laws (*rules pathway*). The Paris Agreement, albeit legally binding (*rules pathway*), primarily relies on the norms and discourses pathway due to enforcement constraints of international law. Thus, countries abide mainly due to the UN's normative power rather than by fear of punishment (*norms and discourses pathway*).

Non-legally binding instruments under public law primarily rely on soft intervention logics based on norms and discourses (e.g., fighting climate change), market incentives (e.g., trade liberalization), market disincentives (e.g., normative pressure), and information and resources (e.g., development cooperation). At the same time, they frequently rely on synergies with other legally binding instruments (e.g., international and national socio-environmental laws and existing national tools and mechanisms, which can assist in data verification and compliance (*rules pathway*)).

At the international level, the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework primarily relies on the norms and discourses pathway, supported by other non-legally binding mechanisms (e.g., development cooperation) (*information & resources pathway*). At the transnational level, private regulation (i.e., certification, bans, moratoria) and industry self-regulation (e.g., deforestation-free pledges) primarily rely on market incentives (e.g., promotion of sustainable consumption) and disincentives (e.g., regional sourcing moratoria) (*markets pathway*). These rely on synergies with legally binding (e.g., supportive public regulatory framework, private contractual agreements) and non-legally binding pathways of influence (e.g., sustainability norms and discourses) (*rules and norms & discourses pathway*). Unlike EU-partner country FLEGT-VPAs, EU-partner country Forest Partnerships are development cooperation-based instruments without trade elements primarily relying on the information and resources pathway (e.g., capacity building, investments). They are supported by legally binding (e.g., mandatory cooperation under the EUDR) and non-legally binding pathways of influence (e.g., socio-environmental protection norms, investments). At the (sub-)national level, the Belém Declaration and Interstate Consortium for the Sustainable Development of the Legal Amazon primarily rely on the norms and discourses pathway.

Theoretically, and building on Sotirov et al. 2020, we contribute to the state-of-the-art research on the pathways of influence framework (Bernstein & Cashore, 2012) by empirically analyzing the designed pathways of influence of a range of international, transnational, and (sub-)national policies and governance mechanisms across key FERC demand-side (i.e., EU) and supply-side (i.e., Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon) regions. Our results also support closing knowledge gaps concerning interactions of different pathways within and across different policies and governance mechanisms and their direction of influence.

Importantly, we show that further developing the “direct access pathway”

towards a more encompassing “information and resources” pathway is possible and necessary to analyze demand-side and supply-side policies and governance mechanisms with different directions of influence (i.e., domestic vs. demand-side to supply-side vs. supply-side to demand-side) (cf. Marques & Eberlein, 2021; Schleifer, 2023; van der Ven et al., 2021).

Last, but not least, our analysis of theories of change of key public policies and private governance mechanisms has some implications for the role of gender and diversity. As shown above, gender and diversity supportive discourse and norms resting on theories of change rooted in sociology and constructivism (‘S’) can be found in only few but key policies such as the EUDR (and partly EUTR, EU FLEGT VPAs). If fully applied in line with their designed intentions, those policies would improve indigenous peoples' rights by supporting more rights of those oppressed like women and supporting more diversity among actors compared to the more powerful mainstream stakeholders (government, economy both dominated by men). The role of civil society, often women led and acting on behalf of those oppressed, could also be strengthened through the empowerment tool of substantiated concerns in the EUDR (partly designed in the EUTR and the FLEGT VPAs.). The questions still remain to what extent and why and how gender and diversity would be supported in the transformative change processes arising from the interplay of public and private regulations at the international, EU, and national levels.

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

This report analyzed the designed and expected theory of change of key policies and governance mechanisms regulating legal and/or sustainable forest and ecosystem-risk commodity supply chains across the EU, Brazil, Cameroon, and Gabon. We identified their goals, degrees of compulsion, designed pathways of influence, and unpacked their main intervention logics based on an assessment of how the different intervention logics interact. The next work package 4 report will assess the policy (in)coherence of selected public and private policies and governance mechanisms. We will zoom into the selected policies and governance mechanisms to identify opportunities (e.g., synergies) and threats (e.g., cooptation and competition) to their theories of change through designed (in)coherences. We do so by examining the character of interaction of the EUDR with selected supply-side policies and governance mechanisms (e.g., Brazil, Cameroon, Gabon public forest laws, Brazil Amazon Soy Moratorium). Reports in work package 5 will then zoom into analyzing the early implementation of the EUDR to assess ongoing and expected behavioral changes and strategies of target actors (e.g., corporate actors, enforcement agencies) in response to the EUDR. We thereby assess opportunities and shortcomings in how the EUDR’s designed theory of change facilitates or hinders the achievement of desired and expected policy outcomes (e.g., deforestation and forest degradation reductions).

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